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D1.1.T-matrix of spheres and pillars

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D.1.1: T-matrix of spheres and pillars

WP1. T.1.1: Modelling of phononic surfaces

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Dynamo. D1.1. T-matrix of spheres and pillars

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4. Introduction

4.1. Executive Summary

In this document we discuss the possible approaches to speed up the computation of the eigenmodes of phononic architectures. The initial proposal in the project was the use of multiple scattering theory, thus the first task to do is the development of expressions and algorithms for the computation of the T-matrix and Green's functions of different resonators (spheres or cylinders) under certain scenarios (semi-infinite plane, free standing plate, layer over a substrate, etc.).

However, we found this approach extremely complex for scatterers with a finite cross section, like holes or cylinders, and we are exploring other possibilities.

Due to the large number of equations involved in the development of the theory, in this document we add just a summary of the methods and our conclusions, and the equations are formulated in the attached document.

It must be pointed out that the objective of this first task was to setup the numerical problem, and the effective solutions of the different geometries is the second task of the WP.

4.2. Relation to Other Project Documents

The present document is related with the following documents:

- Extended version of Deliverable 1.1 T-matrix of spheres and pillars
- Deliverable 1.2: Formulation of multiple scattering
- Deliverable 1.3: Equations of eigenvalues of twisted membranes
- Chaunsali, R., Chen, C. W., & Yang, J. (2018). Subwavelength and directional control of flexural waves in zone-folding induced topological plates. *Physical Review B*, 97(5), 054307.
- Boechler, N., Eliason, J. K., Kumar, A., Maznev, A. A., Nelson, K. A., & Fang, N. (2013). Interaction of a contact resonance of microspheres with surface acoustic waves. *Physical review letters*, 111(3), 036103.

4.3. Abbreviation List

The following acronyms will be used in the present document:

- SAWs: Surface-Acoustic Waves
- BICs: Bound State in Continuum

5. First approach

The samples to be fabricated and characterized during the execution of Dynamo are especially complex to study theoretically. The reason of that is that they will contain many scatterers for surface acoustic waves (SAWs) arranged in quasi-periodic or random patterns. Furthermore, the scatterers – under certain conditions (e.g., at high frequencies) – may exhibit mode-direction-dependent scattering properties. Consequently, the widely used theory of periodic structures

(with Bloch theorem as the basis) is not suitable in the study of these samples, as are some of the techniques based on the point impedance models. Hence, a different approach must be employed.

The first proposal in Dynamo, given the expertise of the theoreticians of the consortium, was to develop a multiple scattering theory version for these waves. This theory has been successfully applied for the study of complex arrangements of scatterers for flexural waves, and we considered that its extension to more complicated types of SAWs might be straightforward.

6. T Matrix of scatterers attached to an elastic surface

The first step towards the development of this theory is the derivation of an analytical expression for the T-matrix of a pillar deposited over a thin elastic plate. We already know the scattering properties of point-like resonators, characterized by a couple of parameters (its mass and its spring constant, and – if required – by the damping parameter), so that the most obvious approach is to compute the equivalent mass and spring constant of a pillar and use that simplified discrete model for studying continuous systems (like pillars) within a selected frequency band. Interestingly, in the literature we can find lumped models for thin pillars (neck) with a larger cylindrical head on the topⁱ

$$m_0 = \frac{\pi \rho_h d_h^2 h_h}{4},$$

$$k_0 = \frac{E_n \pi d_n^2}{4 h_n}.$$

or for spheresⁱⁱ, where the mass is taken as the mass of the sphere and the spring constant is experimentally obtained from the resonant frequency of the sphere.

Unfortunately, the neck-head model fails when pillars alone are considered, and it is obvious that the neck-head structure is much more complex to fabricate at the nanoscale, so that an alternative model might be found.

In a forthcoming publication will be found the derivation of the equations for the effective mass and spring constant of a pillar attached to a thin elastic plate, which are given below:

$$m_0 = \frac{8 \rho a^2 L}{\pi},$$

$$k_0 = \frac{2 E \pi a^2}{L}.$$

We have successfully applied this model in the design of special clusters of scatterers capable of sustaining the so-called Bound States in the continuum (BICs), and we are working now on an experimental demonstration of these states.

In the above result we have considered that the pillars only oscillate longitudinally (compressional mode) however our experience shows that pillars also oscillate transversely (flexural mode). This complex interaction is the result of the coupled

out-of-plane and in-plane displacements and rotations, which – depending on the assumptions on the substrate model (e.g., Euler-Bernoulli/Timoshenko/Lamb or other models) and the assumptions on the scatterers (e.g., translational/rotational impedances) – requires detailed analysis. Although we have worked on an extension theory to include this movement, the excitation of other plate modes is unavoidable in this situation, and we believe that the theory

will always be incomplete.

Therefore, we concluded that, although the T-matrix will give us excellent results for compressional modes, we could explore other possibilities for more complicated structures. The two possibilities that we will consider are briefly explained below. The first one has given excellent results for photonics and acoustics, while the second one has given excellent results for photonics.

7. Mode matching approach

The mode matching method is a semi-analytical theory which allows to simplify considerably the search of eigenmode of complex structures whose solutions we know individually. For instance, in the figure below we have a cluster of scatterers attached to a homogeneous layer which has a generally inhomogeneous substrate at the bottom:

We can assume that we know the solution for the elastic field in each domain of the figure. The mode matching method works on the boundaries connecting the different domains to “match” boundary conditions and find a general solution for the joint domain. The great advantage of this method is that if in the scatterers there is only one excitation (as is usually the case) we can reduce the eigenvalue equation to a system of $N \times N$ equations, with N being the number of scatterers. This reduces dramatically the numerical complexity of the problem, and convergence can be even faster than with the multiple scattering theory.

Thus, this will be the strategy that we will follow within the next months for deliverable D1.2 (deadline February 2024).

8. Guided mode expansion method

When the scatterers patterning the surfaces are holes instead of deposited pillars or spheres, neither the T-matrix approach nor the mode-matching method are suitable for their study. The former because a multipolar theory is required, the latter because there is no field inside the holes and propagation of waves occurs only through the substrate. In this specific case, we found in the literature an alternative method which has been successfully employed in photonics but still needs some optimization for being properly used in elastodynamics.

The fundamental idea consists in expanding the solution of the elastic field as a linear combination of eigenmodes of the substrate without inclusions, and then solve the system either variationally or by the plane wave expansion method (for periodic structures). The convergence is found to be faster given that boundary conditions at the top of the plates are already satisfied.

We will try to generalize this method to other type of substrates, since so far it has been applied only to Lamb waves.

9. Extended version

An extended version is attached to this deliverable. The aim of this document is to develop analytical models for analysis of wave scattering from an arrangement of reflectors - for both surface and guided elastic waves. Within the developed tools and methods, we intend to include multiple scattering-based and also alternative methods for describing scatterers' interactions with the wavefield.

ⁱ Chaunsali, R., Chen, C. W., & Yang, J. (2018). Subwavelength and directional control of flexural waves in zone-folding induced topological plates. *Physical Review B*, 97(5), 054307.

ⁱⁱBoechler, N., Eliason, J. K., Kumar, A., Maznev, A. A., Nelson, K. A., & Fang, N. (2013). Interaction of a contact resonance of microspheres with surface acoustic waves. *Physical review letters*, 111(3), 036103.

DYNAMO/Extended Version of Deliverable D1.1

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Abstract

In this document we outline and analyze methods and algorithms for solving wave propagation problems that involve a substrate medium - in the form of a layer, multiple layers and/or a half space - and a set of objects that scatter incoming and multiply reflected and refracted waves. The role of these objects is to manipulate wave propagation (i.e. energy flow) in a desired way. We consider various models for the scatterers - starting from point-like scatterers described by simple 1-DOF systems, more complex M-DOF systems with the aim of reproducing dynamics of more complex reflectors, finally analyzing continuous structures of finite size like pillars, whose dynamic responses may include multiple resonances, complex displacement fields and directional effects wave propagation. The aim of this document is to develop analytical models for analysis of wave scattering from an arrangement of reflectors - for both surface and guided elastic waves. Within the developed tools and methods we intend to include multiple scattering-based and also alternative methods for describing scatterers' interactions with the wavefield.

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1 Introduction

The computation of the eigenvalues of clusters of resonators attached to an elastic surface is a challenging problem which can be solved analytically only for a few situations with strong simplifications. In most of the cases, numerical methods, like FEM, are required. However, these methods are based on very heavy calculations whose computation time grows up exponentially with the complexity of the problem, and for large clusters of resonators (like the ones found in Dynamo), this calculation is almost impossible.

The objective of these notes is to provide a report of all the semi-analytical solutions for this problem proposed during the first year of the project, in which we have collected several methods, some of them found on the literature, but others developed by the researchers of Dynamo.

Figure 1: Fundamental geometry to be used in Dynamo.

The general geometry is shown in figure [1](#). We will assume that we have a homo-

geneous layer deposited over a generally inhomogeneous substrate, and that over the layer we will have attached a cluster of N resonators. We can assume that these N resonators are periodically distributed in 1D or 2D regular lattices over the surface, in a quasi-periodic fashion or in a random way, and we will need different numerical methods for each of these situations.

Also, although the preferred geometry for the project is the attached resonator, we aim to explore as well the inclusion in one of the layers, since this geometry will keep the mode's symmetry (this is specially relevant for plate modes) and in some occasions can simplify the calculations.

Within the next sections we will formulate all our hypothesis, and during the second year of the project we will solve these equations and will check which one of these methods is the most suitable for our project.

2 Point resonators in beams and plates

Thin beams and plates are of particular interest to the scope of the project. These model structures can serve as substrates supporting flexural waves and clusters of resonators. In other sections of this report we have outlined wave propagation in plates and scattering from finite-size objects. In this section we report on wave interaction with scatterers which in-plane dimensions are much smaller than the wavelength, i.e. with point-like scatterers.

For thin flexural systems, like beams and plates, the single-mode approximations are typically used, namely the Euler-Bernoulli and Kirchoff approximations, respectively. In these models the only DOF is the vertical displacement, hence the simplest boundary condition that may be applied is the one of prescribed point displacement or force. We report on translational point resonators in Sec. 2.1 their clusters on beams in Sec. 2.2 and on plates in Sec. 2.3. The scatterers' clusters on beams are aimed at investigating wave interactions in 1-D systems, while clusters on plates allow for analysis of 2-D configurations and directional properties.

It is interesting to note that the governing equations for beams and plates are fourth-order PDEs, opposite to the classical second-order versions for waves in elastic spaces. As a consequence, mechanical energy can be transferred through a pinned point in a beam or plate through rotations. We comment on rotational resonators in Sec. 2.4, where we propose a set of point resonators (dipoles and quadrupoles) to model force-pairs and therefore control rotations of the medium.

2.1 Translational point resonators

A translational point resonator interacts with the substrate (e.g. beam, plate) through a point force which value depends on mechanical properties of the scatterer and the displacement of the substrate at the attachment point. Two simplest discrete models of resonators are shown in Fig. 2. In both cases the force on the plate (or beam) depends on the mass and stiffness of the attachment (and will depend on the damping force for a case of a damped resonator). It is a common practice to describe the force of the resonator through its (displacement-related) impedance μ defined as $\mu = f/w$, where f denotes the driving force. The displacement-related impedance as used here is analogous to that for acoustics (pressure/velocity) although the two are not dimensionally equivalent. Two possible configurations are

$$\mu = \begin{cases} m_1\omega^2 - \kappa_1 + i\omega\nu_1, & (a), \\ \left(\frac{1}{m_1\omega^2} - \frac{1}{\kappa_1 - i\omega\nu_1}\right)^{-1}, & (b). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where (a) corresponds to the configuration illustrated in Fig. 2a, while (b) to that of Fig. 2b.

Please note that Eq. (1) allows for obtaining a wide range of impedances. For instance for $\mu \rightarrow \infty$ the beam is pinned at the attachment point. Various combinations and connections of the two basic models are also possible, for instance the (a) and (b) models may be attached in parallel, e.g. on either side of the beam, to give $\mu = \mu_a + \mu_b$.

Figure 2: Two basic discrete models of translational impedances.

Other structural configurations, leading to more complex impedance-frequency characteristics, are possible as shown in [1]. Please note that such configurations can be used as M-DOF approximations of continuous systems.

2.2 Clusters of resonators on beams

We first consider a set of N translational impedances, μ_α , on a beam located at positions x_α . The beam has bending stiffness $D (= EI)$ and density ρ' per unit length. We assume the time harmonic motion of the form $e^{-i\omega t}$. The wavenumber k is defined by $k^4 = \omega^2 \rho' / D$.

For the Euler-Bernoulli approximation, the total displacement w satisfies [2]

$$D \left(\frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - k^4 w \right) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \mu_\alpha w(x_\alpha) \delta(x - x_\alpha), \quad (2)$$

with the solution given as

$$w(x) = w_{\text{in}}(x) + \sum_{\beta=1}^N G(x - x_\beta) \mu_\beta w(x_\beta), \quad (3)$$

where $w_{\text{in}}(x)$ is the incident wave, and the Green's function satisfies

$$D \left(\frac{d^4 G(x)}{dx^4} - k^4 G(x) \right) = \delta(x). \quad (4)$$

Following [2], we adopt the normalization procedure so that the impedances and the Green's function are nondimensional, namely

$$m_\alpha = \frac{2Dk^3}{\mu_\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

$$g(x) = 2Dk^3 G(x) = \frac{i}{2}(e^{ik|x|} + ie^{-k|x|}), \quad (6)$$

then (3) becomes

$$w(x) = w_{\text{in}}(x) + \sum_{\beta=1}^N g(x - x_\beta) m_\beta^{-1} w(x_\beta). \quad (7)$$

The solution procedure for a cluster of scatterers on a beam consist in setting $x = x_\alpha$ in (7) resulting in a system of N linear equations. The solution yields

$$w(x) = w_{\text{in}}(x) + \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^N g(x - x_\alpha) M_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} w_{\text{in}}(x_\beta), \quad (8)$$

where $M_{\alpha\beta}^{-1}$ denotes the $\alpha\beta^{\text{th}}$ element of the inverse of the $N \times N$ matrix with elements

$$M_{\alpha\beta} = m_\alpha \delta_{\alpha\beta} - g(x_\alpha - x_\beta). \quad (9)$$

In order to solve the problem defined as in (8), we assume the incident wave of the form

$$w_{\text{in}}^\pm(x) = e^{\pm ikx}, \quad (10)$$

where the \pm sign refers to the incidence side from the left and right, w_{in}^+ and w_{in}^- , respectively. The corresponding reflection coefficients R_+ , R_- and the transmission coefficient T for a cluster of N scatterers on a beam are given by

$$w(x) = \begin{cases} w_{\text{in}}^+ + R_+ e^{-ikx}, & x \rightarrow -\infty, \\ w_{\text{in}}^- + R_- e^{ikx}, & x \rightarrow +\infty, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$w(x) = T e^{\pm ikx}, \quad x \rightarrow \pm\infty \text{ for } w_{\text{in}}^\pm. \quad (12)$$

The particular coefficients depend on the configuration of the cluster, i.e. positions of the scatterers, x_α , and their impedances, μ_α , as

$$R_\pm = \frac{i}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^N M_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} e^{\pm ik(x_\alpha + x_\beta)}, \quad (13)$$

$$T = 1 + \frac{i}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^N M_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} e^{ik(x_\alpha - x_\beta)}. \quad (14)$$

For cluster of scatterers with dissipative properties, the absorption of the cluster (direction-dependent) can be given as

$$\alpha^\pm = 1 - |T|^2 - |R_\pm|^2. \quad (15)$$

Please note that for a non-dissipative cluster $R_+ = R_-$ and $|T|^2 + |R|^2 = 1$, hence $\alpha^+ = \alpha^- = 0$.

The simplest setup consists of a single-scatterer. Without loss of generality we assume the scatterer is placed at $x = 0$. Then $R_\pm = R = \frac{i}{2}(m - g(0))^{-1}$ and $T = 1 + R$. The impedance of the scatterer, resulting in the designed (selected) transmission coefficient is given by

$$m = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{iT}{2(T-1)} \Rightarrow w(0) = -i + (1+i)T. \quad (16)$$

One can clearly observe that for infinite impedance $\mu \rightarrow \infty \Rightarrow m = 0$ and $w(0) = 0$. Hence, the attachment point is pinned. It can be seen from (16) that for this case half of the incident wave energy is transmitted and half is reflected, i.e. $|R| = |T| = 1/\sqrt{2}$. This means that despite the scatterer constrains the vertical movement of the beam, the energy is still transferred through the attachment point via rotations. Interestingly, the scatterer can be tuned to prevent transmission, $T = 0$ for $m = -\frac{1}{2}$.

For a cluster of two scatterers, i.e. $N = 2$, spaced by a distance a (e.g. at $x_1 = -\frac{a}{2}$ and $x_2 = \frac{a}{2}$) the matrix \mathbf{M} is

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 - g(0) & -g(a) \\ -g(a) & m_2 - g(0) \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

resulting in the reflection and transmission coefficients of the form

$$R_\pm = \frac{i}{2 \det \mathbf{M}} \left(m_1 e^{\pm ika} + m_2 e^{\mp ika} - 2g(0) \cos ka + 2g(a) \right), \quad (18)$$

$$T = 1 + \frac{i}{2 \det \mathbf{M}} \left(m_1 + m_2 - 2g(0) + 2g(a) \cos ka \right). \quad (19)$$

Writing the two, direction-specific, reflection coefficients in the explicit form gives

$$R_\pm = \frac{g^2(0)}{\det \mathbf{M}} \left(e^{-ka} + \sin ka - \cos ka - (m_1 + m_2) \cos ka \pm i(m_2 - m_1) \sin ka \right). \quad (20)$$

Interestingly, as shown in [2], Eq. (20) indicates that in order for the reflection to be symmetric, namely $|R_+| = |R_-|$ the two impedances must be real.

2.3 Clusters of resonators on plates

In this section we consider clusters of point-like scatterers on a 2-D thin plate. We assume the plate has h , bending stiffness $D (= EI/(1 - \nu^2))$ and density ρ . Assuming time harmonic motion of the form $e^{-i\omega t}$, the flexural wavenumber k reads $k^4 = \omega^2 \rho h / D$.

The cluster of point scatterers considered in this section consists of N point scatterers positioned at \mathbf{R}_α with individual impedances t_α . We denote the total displacement as ψ and define the governing equation for this scattering problem as [3]

$$D(\Delta^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}) - k^4 \psi(\mathbf{r})) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N t_\alpha \psi(\mathbf{R}_\alpha) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_\alpha). \quad (21)$$

The point scatterers are defined in the same way as before and they are assumed as translational impedances t .

The Green's function for the plate problem is given as the particular solution for $\psi = G$ and for a single source of the form $\delta(\mathbf{r})$ on the right hand side of (21) yields

$$G(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{i}{8k^2 D} \left(H_0^{(1)}(kr) - H_0^{(1)}(ikr) \right). \quad (22)$$

Assuming an incident field ψ_0 arriving at a cluster of N point-like scatterers, the total wavefield $\psi(\mathbf{r})$ is given as the sum of the incident and the scattered fields,

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}) = \psi_0(\mathbf{r}) + \psi_s(\mathbf{r}). \quad (23)$$

Then, the scattered field yields

$$\psi_s(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N B_\beta G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_\beta), \quad (24)$$

with $G(\mathbf{r}) = G(|\mathbf{r}|)$ being the Green's function. The coefficients B_β are obtained from the multiple scattering equation defined as [3]

$$\sum_{\beta=1}^N [t_\beta^{-1} \delta_{\alpha\beta} - G(\mathbf{R}_\alpha - \mathbf{R}_\beta)] B_\beta = \psi_0(\mathbf{R}_\alpha). \quad (25)$$

where each equation (25) is evaluated at scatterers' positions. This approach results in a system of N equations in N unknowns. The quantity t_α represents the strength of the α^{th} scatterer and it is characteristic of the physical properties of the scatterer. This direct multiple scattering problem consists in defining the number of scatterers,

N , their strengths t_α and locations \mathbf{R}_β . Subsequently, we compute the B_α coefficients to determine the wavefield in the plate.

The design of a cluster for obtaining desired properties of the wavefield can be set up as follows. The target (desired) wavefield is expressed as a linear combination of basis functions ϕ_n of the form

$$\psi_s(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n \phi_n(\mathbf{r}). \quad (26)$$

Now, one needs to select the number N_p of A_n coefficients, so that - according to (26) - the scattered field resulting from the metacluster will have the desired approximated radiation pattern in the far-field. In this problem, there will exist a matrix S

$$A_n = \sum_{\beta=1}^N S_{n\beta} B_\beta. \quad (27)$$

In the next step, one needs to decide on the number of scatterers in the cluster, N . In case $N = N_p$ Eq. (27) generates a system of N equations in N unknowns. From this set we can solve for the B_β coefficients. After this first step, one can obtain t_α from Eq. (26) as

$$t_\alpha^{-1} = \frac{1}{B_\alpha} \left(\psi_0(\mathbf{R}_\alpha) + \sum_{\beta=1}^N G(\mathbf{R}_\alpha - \mathbf{R}_\beta) B_\beta \right), \quad (28)$$

hence determining the required physical properties of each scatterer.

For waves in thin plates, ψ is the plate deflection in the vertical direction, G is the Green's function, and

$$B_\alpha = t_\alpha \psi(\mathbf{R}_\alpha), \quad (29)$$

is the point force per unit area of scatterer α and t_α is the point impedance of the α^{th} scatterer. We again assume that the time dependence is of the form $e^{-i\omega t}$. Additional constraints, e.g. the requirement of the passivity of the cluster, can be introduced in the inverse problem.

The direct far field solution is computed in the following way. First, the functions ϕ_n of (26) are selected as the infinite set

$$\phi_n(\mathbf{r}) = G(\mathbf{r}) e^{in\theta}, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (30)$$

where the position is given in the polar coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (r, \theta)$. Please note that with this configuration the coefficients A_n of (26) can be seen as the far field amplitudes of

the scattered wavefield. This is readily seen by realizing that the far-field scattering pattern for a source at $\mathbf{R}_\beta = (R_\beta, \theta_\beta)$ is

$$G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_\beta) \approx G(\mathbf{r})e^{-ikR_\beta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}. \quad (31)$$

The scattered far-field wavefield of the cluster follows from (24) and (31) as

$$\psi_s(\mathbf{r}) \approx G(\mathbf{r})f(\theta), \quad (32)$$

with the far-field radiation function

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N B_\beta e^{-ikR_\beta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}. \quad (33)$$

Alternatively,

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n e^{in\theta}, \quad (34)$$

where the (infinite) set of coefficients $\{A_n\}$ is related to the N coefficients $\{B_\beta\}$ through (27) as

$$S_{n\beta} = (-i)^n e^{-in\theta_\beta} J_n(kR_\beta). \quad (35)$$

Applications examples for this theory have been presented in [4] along with the inverse analysis leading to the design procedure for metaclusters of point scatterers.

2.4 Rotational resonators on beams as multipoles

As stated before, the point scatterers exert a vertical force on the beam they are attached to. For infinite impedance, they restrict the movement of the beam but this case does not result in the full reflection of the flexural wave. Instead the incoming energy is split into half of the energy being reflected and half being transmitted. This energy partition occurs due to the inability of a pinned point to restrict rotations of the beam around the fixed point of attachment. This section discusses the derivation of a rotational point scatterer (or an approximation of it).

For a beam loaded by a moment M (applied in the counter-clockwise direction) at $x = 0$, the following assumptions are made for the wavefields on the left and right to the point of application

$$w_L(x) = a_L e^{-ikx} + b_L e^{+kx}, \quad (36)$$

$$w_R(x) = a_R e^{+ikx} + b_R e^{-kx}. \quad (37)$$

With the displacement field of the form of Eqs. (36) we enforce the displacement continuity

$$w_L(0) = w_R(0) \rightarrow a_L + b_L = a_R + b_R, \quad (38)$$

slope continuity

$$\frac{dw_L(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=0} = \frac{dw_R(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=0} \rightarrow -ia_L + b_L = ia_R - b_R, \quad (39)$$

moment balance

$$EI \frac{d^2 w_L(x)}{dx^2}\Big|_{x=0} = M + EI \frac{d^2 w_R(x)}{dx^2}\Big|_{x=0} \rightarrow -a_L + b_L = \frac{M}{EI k^2} - a_R + b_R, \quad (40)$$

and the shear forces balance

$$\frac{d^3 w_L(x)}{dx^3}\Big|_{x=0} = \frac{d^3 w_R(x)}{dx^3}\Big|_{x=0} \rightarrow ia_L + b_L = -ia_R - b_R. \quad (41)$$

The set of Eqs. (38)-(41) comprises of four equations in four unknowns. Solving the system yields

$$a_L = -\frac{M}{4EI k^2}, \quad (42)$$

$$b_L = \frac{M}{4EI k^2}, \quad (43)$$

$$a_R = \frac{M}{4EI k^2}, \quad (44)$$

$$b_R = -\frac{M}{4EI k^2}. \quad (45)$$

Consequently, using Eqs. (36) the Green's function for a beam loaded with concentrated moment is given by

$$G(x, k) = \text{sign}(x) \frac{M}{4EI k^2} (e^{ik|x|} - e^{-k|x|}). \quad (46)$$

With the Green's function of the form of Eq. (46), the multiple scattering problem with rotational scatterers can be solved.

3 Scattering properties of a pillar attached to a thin elastic plate

For plates very thin compared to the wavelength, the Kirchhoff plate approximation, i.e. single-mode approximation, can be employed. This model greatly simplifies the problem allowing for explicit analytical solutions. The wave equation for flexural waves in a thin plate, of thickness h , density ρ and bending stiffness D_b , loaded with a distributed force $q(\mathbf{r})$ is given by [5]

$$(\nabla^4 - k_b^4)W(\mathbf{r}) = -q(\mathbf{r})/D_b, \quad (47)$$

with $k_b^4 = \rho h \omega^2 / D_b$. The solution to (47) can be given in terms of the Green's function,

$$W(\mathbf{r}) = W_0(\mathbf{r}) - \iint_S q(\mathbf{r}')/D_b G_0(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')dS, \quad (48)$$

where $W_0(\mathbf{r})$ is the incident field and the surface S is the surface where the load q has been applied. As long as the source generating this incident field is such that $|\mathbf{r}_S| > |\mathbf{r}|$, as is the case for a scattering problem, we can express the incident field in the basis of the regular solutions of the wave equation, thus

$$W_0(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_q [A_q^J J_q(k_b r) + A_q^I I_q(k_b r)] e^{iq\theta}, \quad (49)$$

The Green's function can be expanded as

$$G_0(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') = \frac{i}{8k_b^2} \sum_q [J_q(k_b r_<) e^{-iq\theta'} H_q(k_b r_>) + \frac{2i}{\pi} I_q(k_b r_<) e^{-iq\theta'} K_q(k_b r_>)] e^{iq\theta}, \quad (50)$$

with $r_<$ and $r_>$ being the smaller and larger of r and r' , respectively. For a circularly symmetric resonator, the surface S will be a circle of radius a , then we get, for $|\mathbf{r}| > a$

$$W(\mathbf{r}) = W_0(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_q [B_q^H H_q(k_b r) + B_q^K K_q(k_b r)] e^{iq\theta}, \quad (51)$$

where

$$B_q^H = -\frac{i}{8D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^a q(\mathbf{r}') J_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta, \quad (52)$$

$$B_q^K = \frac{1}{4\pi D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^a q(\mathbf{r}') I_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta, \quad (53)$$

while for $|\mathbf{r}| < a$ we have

$$W(\mathbf{r}) = W_0(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_q [C_q^J(r)J_q(k_b r) + C_q^I(r)I_q(k_b r) + C_q^H(r)H_q(k_b r) + C_q^K(r)K_q(k_b r)] e^{iq\theta}, \quad (54)$$

where

$$C_q^J(r) = -\frac{i}{8D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_r^a q(\mathbf{r}') H_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta, \quad (55)$$

$$C_q^I(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_r^a q(\mathbf{r}') K_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta, \quad (56)$$

$$C_q^H(r) = -\frac{i}{8D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^r q(\mathbf{r}') J_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta, \quad (57)$$

$$C_q^K(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi D_b k_b^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^r q(\mathbf{r}') I_q(k_b r') e^{-iq\theta'} r' dr' d\theta. \quad (58)$$

Note that since $B_q^H = C_q^H(a)$ and $B_q^K = C_q^K(a)$, and that $C_q^J(a) = C_q^I(a) = 0$, the field is continuous at $r = a$, and it can be easily shown that the first and second derivatives are continuous as well.

Therefore, once we know the distribution of the load $q(\mathbf{r})$, the problem can be completely solved. In what follows, we assume that the load is given by the traction field on the plate exerted by the pillar. Hence, $q(\mathbf{r})$ acts on the contact surface between the pillar and the plate. This traction arises as a result of the vertical displacement of the plate $W(\mathbf{r})$, therefore, analogously to the classical multiple scattering theory, the coefficients B_q^i are directly related to A_q^i coefficients, i.e., coefficients of the incident field, defining in this way the T matrix of the pillar.

As the only displacement component in this model of the plate is the vertical, z , displacement, the pillar or the attached resonator and the plate display the same displacement field $W(\mathbf{r})$ over S . The displacement of the resonator at $z = 0$ will be can be expanded as a Fourier series

$$W_p(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_q W_q f_q(r, \omega) e^{iq\theta}, \quad (59)$$

following Eqs. (59), (54) and (49) the displacement continuity condition will read

$$W_q f_q(r, \omega) = A_q^J J_q(k_b r) + A_q^I I_q(k_b r) + C_q^J(r) J_q(k_b r) + C_q^I(r) I_q(k_b r) + C_q^H(r) H_q(k_b r) + C_q^K(r) K_q(k_b r). \quad (60)$$

The corresponding out-of-plane stress component of the mode will be

$$\sigma_{zz} = \sum_q W_q Z_q(\omega) f_q(r, \omega) e^{iq\theta}. \quad (61)$$

where $Z_q(\omega)$ will be the complex impedance of the mode, which will depend on the resonator's geometry in the most general case. The most common situation is that the functions $f_q(r, \omega)$ be, for small ωr , powers of ωr of order q , thus the coefficients $C_q^i(r)$ from (60) will be

$$C_q^J(r) = -\frac{i\pi Z_q(\omega)\omega^q W_q}{4D_b k_b^2} \int_r^a H_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (62)$$

$$C_q^I(r) = \frac{Z_q(\omega)\omega^q W_q}{2D_b k_b^2} \int_r^a K_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (63)$$

$$C_q^H(r) = -\frac{i\pi Z_q(\omega)\omega^q W_q}{4D_b k_b^2} \int_0^r J_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (64)$$

$$C_q^K(r) = \frac{g_q(\omega)\omega^q Z_q}{2D_b k_b^2} \int_0^r I_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (65)$$

so that we can solve for W_q as a function of A_q^i

$$W_q = \frac{J_q(k_b r)}{\omega^q r^q - \sum_X Z_q(\omega) m_q^X X_q(k_b r)} A_q^J + \frac{I_q(k_b r)}{\omega^q r^q - \sum_X Z_q(\omega) m_q^X X_q(k_b r)} A_q^I, \quad (66)$$

with $X = J, I, H, K$ and

$$m_q^J(r) = -\frac{i\pi\omega^q}{4D_b k_b^2} \int_r^a H_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (67)$$

$$m_q^I(r) = \frac{\omega^q}{2D_b k_b^2} \int_r^a K_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (68)$$

$$m_q^H(r) = -\frac{i\pi\omega^q}{4D_b k_b^2} \int_0^r J_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr', \quad (69)$$

$$m_q^K(r) = \frac{\omega^q}{2D_b k_b^2} \int_0^r I_q(k_b r')(r')^{q+1} dr'. \quad (70)$$

In the low frequency limit ($k_b r \ll 1$) the behaviour of both J_q and I_q with the radius is the same, and proportional to $k_b^q r^q$. Hence, we expect the same for $\sum_X m_q^X X_q(k_b r)$, and assume in this limit the relationship of W_q and C_q coefficients as

$$W_q = \chi_q(\omega) A_q^J + \chi_q(\omega) A_q^I, \quad (71)$$

being

$$\chi_q(\omega) = \lim_{k_b r \ll 1} \frac{\frac{(k_b r)^q}{q! 2^q}}{r^q \omega^q - \omega^q Z_q(\omega) \sum_X m_q^X X_q(k_b r)}. \quad (72)$$

After elementary integration of the special functions (see eq.[WA 132(1)] in [6]) and some algebra, it can be seen that

$$\sum_X m_q^X X_q(k_b r) \approx -\frac{r^q}{2D_b k_b^4} \left(2 - \frac{i\pi k_b^{q+1} a^{q+1}}{q! 2^{q+1}} (H_{q+1}(k_b a) - 2i/\pi K_{q+1}(k_b a)) \right). \quad (73)$$

Showing that, as expected, the quantity $\chi_q(\omega)$ is independent of the radial coordinate r . The above developments lead to the B_q coefficients in the form

$$B_q^H = \chi_q(\omega) Z_q(\omega) m_q^H(a) (A_q^J + A_q^I), \quad (74)$$

$$B_q^K = \chi_q(\omega) Z_q(\omega) m_q^K(a) (A_q^J + A_q^I). \quad (75)$$

Consequently, the T matrix of the resonator yields

$$T = \chi_q(\omega) g_q(\omega) \begin{pmatrix} m_q^H(a) & m_q^H(a) \\ m_q^K(a) & m_q^K(a) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (76)$$

Therefore the solution for the T matrix requires the calculation of χ and g . We that for symmetries associated with $q = 0, 1, 2$, the quantity m_q will be proportional to a^2 , so that these elements of the matrix be proportional to the area of the contact area of the scatterer.

3.1 Isotropic term of the T matrix ($q = 0$) for a pillar

This section is devoted to the calculation of $Z_0(\omega)$. The pillar is assumed to have circular cross section of radius a and length L . Stress-free conditions are assumed at the external boundaries (except the bottom flat surface connected to the plate).

The simplest description of the compressional mode of the pillar can be done by means of the rod equation [7]

$$\rho_a \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial t^2} = E_a \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \quad (77)$$

and

$$\sigma_{zz} = E_a \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \quad (78)$$

If stress-free boundary conditions are applied at $z = L$ the solution of the above equation is

$$u_z = u_0 \cos k_a(z - L), \quad (79)$$

$$\sigma_{zz} = -u_0 k_a E_a \sin k_a(z - L), \quad (80)$$

with $k_a = \omega/c_a$ and $c_a = \sqrt{E_a/\rho_a}$. The above expressions allow us to identify the $Z_0(\omega)$ term as

$$Z_0(\omega) = -\omega\sqrt{\rho_a E_a} \tan k_a L. \quad (81)$$

3.2 T Matrix

To compute the $\chi_0(\omega)$ coefficient, we still need the following identities

$$\sum_X m_q^X X_q(k_b r) \approx -\frac{1}{2D_b k_b^4} \left(2 - \frac{i\pi k_b a}{2} (H_1(k_b a) - 2i/\pi K_1(k_b a)) \right) \approx \frac{i\pi a^2}{8D_b k_b^2} \quad (82)$$

and

$$m_0^H(a) = -\frac{i\pi a}{4D_b k_b^3} J_1(k_b a) \approx -\frac{i\pi a^2}{8D_b k_b^2} \quad (83)$$

Then, the $q = 0$ element of the T matrix, corresponding to the T^{HJ} element, is, after some algebra

$$T_0 = \frac{i\pi a^2}{8D_b k_b^2} \frac{\rho_a \omega^2 \sin k_a L}{k_a \cos k_a L - i\pi a^2 \rho_a \omega^2 \sin k_a L / (8D_b k_b^2)} \quad (84)$$

or, in a more suitable form,

$$T_0 = \frac{i\pi a^2 k_b^2}{8} \frac{\rho_a / \rho_b \sin k_a L}{h k_a \cos k_a L - i\pi a^2 k_b^2 \rho_a / \rho_b \sin k_a L / 8} \quad (85)$$

In the low frequency limit, the above element is

$$T_0 \approx \frac{i\pi k_b^2 a^2}{8} \frac{L \rho_a}{h \rho_b} \quad (86)$$

As expected, it is proportional to $k_b^2 a^2$. Also, the T matrix can be expressed as

$$T_0 = \frac{i}{8k_b^2} \frac{t_0}{1 - it_0/8k_b^2} \quad (87)$$

with

$$t_0 = \frac{\pi a^2 k_b^4}{k_z h} \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_b} \tan k_z L \quad (88)$$

if we use $k_b^4 = \rho_b h / D_b \omega^2$ and the expansion of $\tan z$ around the first pole,

$$\tan z \approx \frac{2z}{\pi^2/4 - z^2} \quad (89)$$

the above expression can be set as

$$t_0 = \frac{8\rho_a a^2 L}{\pi D_b} \frac{\omega_R^2 \omega^2}{\omega_R^2 - \omega^2} \quad (90)$$

with

$$\omega_R = \frac{\pi c_{bar}}{2L} \quad (91)$$

We can compare then this T matrix with that of the mass-spring resonator, for which

$$t_0 = \frac{m_0}{D_b} \frac{\omega_R^2 \omega^2}{\omega_R^2 - \omega^2} \quad (92)$$

so that we can identify

$$m_0 = \frac{8\rho_a a^2 L}{\pi} \approx 0.8m_p \quad (93)$$

where $m_p = \pi a^2 L \rho_a$ is the mass of the pillar. Finally, the spring constant of the resonator is

$$k_0 = \omega_R^2 m_0 = \frac{2E_a \pi a^2}{L} \quad (94)$$

4 Eigenmodes of a periodic distribution of point attachments atop an elastic surface

In the previous section we showed how a small pillar attached to a thin plate can behave as a point-like spring-mass resonator, as long as the vibrational state is the compressional mode of the rod. Although this is only a very specific problem, it is likely that this be the case, and this system has been widely studied in the literature. Here we provide a set of equations generalizing the problem of multiple scattering of mass-spring point-like resonators atop an elastic surface, but solving the full elasticity problem so that we are not limited to a thin plate. Thus, we formulate first the problem for the semi-infinite plane with a periodic distribution of a cluster of resonators and then we give some hints to extend the solution to a waveguide (1D distribution of the cluster) and to the cluster itself isolated. Also, we give the guide to solve the problem of having a bottom boundary, either a rigid or free boundary or with a given substrate.

4.1 Rayleigh waves

The displacement vector of the elastic field will be expanded in three modes propagating along the xy plane with wavenumber $\mathbf{k}_G = \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}$, being the difference between them the component of the wavenumber in the z direction, which is $s\beta_G^\ell$ for $\ell = L, P, S$ and $s = 1$ if we have only one boundary or $s = +, -$ in case of having a bottom boundary where waves are reflected. The polarization L is parallel to the three-dimensional longitudinal wave vector $\mathbf{k}_G^L = \mathbf{k}_G + s\beta_{fG}^L \hat{\mathbf{z}}$, while the P and S are perpendicular to the transverse wave vector $\mathbf{k}_G^T = \mathbf{k}_G + s\beta_{fG}^T \hat{\mathbf{z}}$, with S being contained in the xy plane and perpendicular to P completing the orthogonal set. These polarization vectors are computed as

$$\mathbf{u}_G^L = \frac{1}{k_{LG}} \hat{\mathbf{z}} = \frac{1}{k_L} (\mathbf{k}_G + \beta_{fG}^L \hat{\mathbf{z}}), \quad (95)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_G^S = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{k}_G|} \hat{\mathbf{z}} \times \mathbf{k}_G = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{k}_G|} (-\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_G \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_G \hat{\mathbf{y}}), \quad (96)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_G^P = \frac{1}{k_{TG}} \times \mathbf{u}_G^S = -\frac{\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_G \beta_G^T}{k_T |\mathbf{k}_G|} \hat{\mathbf{x}} - \frac{\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_G \beta_G^T}{k_T |\mathbf{k}_G|} \hat{\mathbf{y}} + \frac{|\mathbf{k}_G|}{k_T} \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (97)$$

Since we are looking for bounded modes at the surface $z = 0$, we set $s = +$ only and assume that the positive region of the z axis is oriented towards the bottom of the page. Given the periodicity of the problem, a summation in all the reciprocal

vectors will be made in order to represent the total displacement field, thus

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \ell} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} T_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}(z) e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad (98)$$

where $T_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}(z) = e^{i\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} z}$.

The components of the stress tensor in the z direction will therefore be 8

$$\sigma_{zz} = i \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \ell} [\lambda(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} + (\lambda + 2\mu)\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}] A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} T_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}(z) e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad (99)$$

$$\sigma_{xz} = i\mu \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \ell} [\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}) \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}] A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} T_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}(z) e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad (100)$$

$$\sigma_{yz} = i\mu \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \ell} [\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}) \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}] A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} T_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}(z) e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{r}}. \quad (101)$$

Since we are considering only compressional modes of the resonators, these will make a force along the vertical direction only, thus the boundary conditions at $z = 0$ will be $\sigma_{xz} = \sigma_{yz} = 0$, therefore

$$\sigma_{xz} = \sum_{\ell} [\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}) \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}] A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} = 0, \quad (102)$$

$$\sigma_{yz} = \sum_{\ell} [\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}) \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell}] A_{\mathbf{G}}^{\ell} = 0. \quad (103)$$

Since $\hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^S = 0$, and $\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^S = 0$, if we multiply the first and second equations by $-\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}$, respectively, and we add them, we find

$$A_{\mathbf{G}}^S = 0, \quad (104)$$

what means that, as it is well known, shear waves cannot be bounded at a free surface. Similarly, if we multiply the first and second equations by $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}$, respectively, and we add them, we find

$$[|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^P + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^P \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^P] A_{\mathbf{G}}^P = - [|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^L + \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L \mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^L] A_{\mathbf{G}}^L, \quad (105)$$

or, after some algebra,

$$A_{\mathbf{G}}^P = -2 \frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L |\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2} k_L} \frac{k_T}{k_L} A_{\mathbf{G}}^L. \quad (106)$$

Therefore, we have that, at $z = 0$,

$$\sigma_{zz}(\mathbf{r}) = i \sum_{\mathbf{G}} [(\lambda k_L + 2\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^L) A_{\mathbf{G}}^L + 2\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^P \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^P A_{\mathbf{G}}^P] e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad (107)$$

and, using the previous equation

$$\sigma_{zz}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{i}{k_L} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \left[\lambda k_L^2 + 2\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{L2} - 4\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^P\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L \frac{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}} \right] A_{\mathbf{G}}^L e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}}. \quad (108)$$

Following [9, 10], the periodic arrangement of resonators placed on the surface of the plate exerts a force given by

$$\sigma_{zz}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{R}_n} \sum_{\alpha} t_{\alpha} \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_{\alpha n}) u_z(\mathbf{R}_{\alpha n}), \quad (109)$$

with t_{α} being the impedance of the scatterer which will be in general a resonant quantity. using

$$u_z(\mathbf{R}_{\alpha n}) = \sum_{\mathbf{G}} (\hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^L A_{\mathbf{G}}^L + \hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^P A_{\mathbf{G}}^P) e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha n}} = -\frac{k_T^2}{k_L} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \left(\frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}} \right) A_{\mathbf{G}}^L e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha n}}, \quad (110)$$

we find, after multiplication by $\exp(-\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}'} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and integration over the unit cell,

$$\frac{i}{k_L} \left[\lambda k_L^2 + 2\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}'}^{L2} - 4\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}'}^T\beta_{\mathbf{G}'}^L \frac{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}'}|^2}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}'}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}'}^{T2}} \right] A_{\mathbf{G}'}^L = -\frac{k_T^2}{k_L} \sum_{\alpha} \frac{t_{\alpha}}{\Omega_c} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \left(\frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}} \right) A_{\mathbf{G}}^L e^{i(\mathbf{G}-\mathbf{G}') \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha}}. \quad (111)$$

We can now define

$$X_{\alpha} = \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \left(\frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}} \right) A_{\mathbf{G}}^L e^{i\mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha}}, \quad (112)$$

and, after repeating the process found in [3], we arrive at the secular equation

$$\sum_{\beta} M_{\alpha\beta} X_{\beta} = 0, \quad (113)$$

with

$$M_{\alpha\beta} = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - t_{\alpha} G_{\alpha\beta}, \quad (114)$$

and

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{ik_T^2}{\Omega_c} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \frac{\frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}}}{\lambda k_L^2 + 2\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{L2} - 4\mu\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^T\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L \frac{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2}{|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}}} e^{i\mathbf{G} \cdot (\mathbf{R}_{\alpha} - \mathbf{R}_{\beta})}, \quad (115)$$

or, after some algebra,

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{ik_T^2}{\Omega_c} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \frac{\beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L e^{i\mathbf{G} \cdot (\mathbf{R}_{\alpha} - \mathbf{R}_{\beta})}}{[(\lambda + 2\mu)k_L^2 - 2\mu|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2] (|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 - \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^{T2}) - 4\mu|\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}}|^2 \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^T \beta_{\mathbf{G}}^L}. \quad (116)$$

Thus, the above equations show that, for a given unit cell and a cluster of N resonators on it, we can obtain the dispersion relation $\omega = \omega(\mathbf{k})$ by solving the secular equation

$$\det M(\omega, \mathbf{k}) = 0 \quad (117)$$

This is the basic problem of this nature to solve and, once this is understood, we can continue towards more specific scenarios, as shown below.

4.2 Waveguides or finite clusters of resonators

In the previous section we have considered the eigenmodes of periodic distributions of finite clusters of scatterers. While this is a straightforward approach to understand either single lattices or complex clusters, if a more rigorous approach wants to be developed to study waveguides or finite clusters, we need to work on the lattice sum (115), since the multiple scattering matrix $M_{\alpha\beta}$ remains unchanged.

Then, if the cluster of resonators is used to form a waveguide along the x direction, we have to make unit cell along the y axis infinite, then the Brillouin zone collapses to zero and the reciprocal lattice vectors $G_y = 2m\pi/L_y$ become a continuous variable, thus we have to make the replacement [3]

$$\frac{1}{\Omega_c} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} F(K_x + G_x, K_y + G_y) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2\pi a} \sum_n \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(K_x + 2n\pi/a, k_y) dk_y. \quad (118)$$

Similarly, if we are interested in the eigenmodes of an isolated cluster, we can make the full unit cell infinite and then the right replacement is

$$\frac{1}{\Omega_c} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} F(K_x + G_x, K_y + G_y) \rightarrow \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(k_x, k_y) dk_x dk_y. \quad (119)$$

4.3 Adding a bottom interface

In the previous two sections we modeled the behaviour of a surface with a periodic or finite distribution of scatters. Since only a semi-infinite plane was considered, we needed evanescent solutions in the z axis. Adding a bottom flat interface with a substrate or even with free space is rather trivial now, since what we need is to build solutions with incoming and forthcoming waves in the z direction and apply boundary conditions at the bottom surface. Since it is assumed to be flat and transversally isotropic the complexity is no other than a classical elasticity problem.

5 Mode-matching for plate modes

Although the system of point-like resonators explained before can be successful under certain conditions, for nanostructured geometries studied in this project are not suitable, since the aspect ratio of the pillars we can build without collapse is small, thus we need to develop a more accurate method to study larger radius cylinders. Mode matching, which is a method extensively used in acoustics [11] and electrodynamics [12] might be a good approach, although for this purpose we need to find some modes with well defined orthogonality relations.

We will begin again with the periodic distribution of scatterers, with lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ which will define a reciprocal vector space \mathbf{G} in the usual way.

Bloch theorem allow us to expand the displacement field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}, z)$ in the substrate as

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}, z) = \sum_{\ell} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} A_{\ell\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{u}_{\ell\mathbf{G}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}} f_{\ell}(z) \quad (120)$$

where $\ell = 1, 2, 3$ runs for the three polarizations of the homogeneous layer which satisfy the corresponding boundary conditions at the interface between the homogeneous layer and the substrate. The phase $\Phi_{\ell\mathbf{G}}$, which can be complex for leaky waves, relates the incident and reflected waves traveling along the z direction.

We will name again resonators as $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Inside the α resonator we will have a set of localized modes satisfying boundary conditions throughout the cavity. Obviously each problem is different, but we expect that, at the intersection connecting the layer and the cavity, we will be able to define a set of modes of the form

$$\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_n B_{\alpha n} \mathbf{u}_{\alpha n}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (121)$$

which we want to form a basis in this area, i.e.,

$$\frac{1}{\Omega_{\alpha}} \iint \mathbf{u}_{\alpha n}^*(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\alpha m}(\mathbf{r}) d\Omega = \delta_{nm} \quad (122)$$

where Ω_{α} is the area that have in common the surface and the resonator.

At $z = 0$ the z component of the stress field in the layer will be given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_{\ell} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} A_{\ell\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{T}_{\ell\mathbf{G}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \quad (123)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{T}_{\ell\mathbf{G}}$ is directly related the $\mathbf{u}_{\ell\mathbf{G}}$. Also, in the cavity we will have

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_n B_{\alpha n} \mathbf{F}_{\alpha n}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (124)$$

where the vectors $\mathbf{F}_{\alpha n}$ has to be computed for each resonator.

The theory of mode matching imposes continuity of the displacement field through the surface of each cavity α , thus

$$B_{\alpha n} = \sum_{\ell} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \chi_{\ell \mathbf{G}}^{\alpha n} A_{\ell \mathbf{G}} \quad (125)$$

where

$$\chi_{\ell \mathbf{G}}^{\alpha n} = \frac{1}{\Omega_{\alpha}} \iint \mathbf{u}_{\alpha n}^*(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \cos(\Phi_{\ell \mathbf{G}}) d\Omega \quad (126)$$

Similarly, the continuity of the z component of the stress field is imposed through the full unit cell, leading to

$$\sum_{\ell} \mathbf{T}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} A_{\ell \mathbf{G}} = \sum_{m, \beta} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\beta m}^{\mathbf{G}} B_{\beta m} \quad (127)$$

where

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_{\alpha n}^{\mathbf{G}} = \frac{1}{\Omega} \iint \mathbf{F}_{\alpha n}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot e^{-i\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{r}} d\Omega \quad (128)$$

Let us assume we find a basis $\mathbf{R}_{\ell \mathbf{G}}$ such that

$$\mathbf{R}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{\ell' \mathbf{G}} = \delta_{\ell \ell'} \quad (129)$$

we will have then

$$A_{\ell \mathbf{G}} = \sum_{m, \beta} \mathbf{R}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\beta m}^{\mathbf{G}} B_{\beta m} \quad (130)$$

So that we can write

$$\sum_{m, \beta} M_{nm}^{\alpha \beta} B_{\beta m} = 0 \quad (131)$$

where

$$M_{nm}^{\alpha \beta} = \delta_{\alpha \beta} \delta_{nm} - \sum_{\mathbf{G}, \ell} \chi_{\ell \mathbf{G}}^{\alpha n} \mathbf{R}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\beta m}^{\mathbf{G}} \quad (132)$$

In case of having an isolated cluster, the above sum becomes an integral in the usual way.

In most of the applications we can assume that, for a short frequency range, only one mode inside the cavity is excited (this approximation is quite successful in acoustics and optics), thus we will have

$$\sum_{\beta} M_{\alpha \beta} B_{\beta} = 0 \quad (133)$$

and

$$M_{nm}^{\alpha \beta} = \delta_{\alpha \beta} - \sum_{\mathbf{G}} \chi_{\mathbf{G}}^{\alpha} \mathbf{R}_{\ell \mathbf{G}} \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}_{\beta}^{\mathbf{G}} \quad (134)$$

The eigenvalue problem reduces then to find the zeros of a matrix of size $N \times N$, whose complexity relies in the above lattice sum. This approach is, however, quite suitable for the computation of resonances of large clusters, since the size of the matrix M will not blow up for a few hundred of them.

6 Guided mode expansion method

The above sections describe several methods for the solution of the problem of scatterers deposited atop an elastic surface. However, we can design nanostructures by inserting inclusions in a thin plate, like air holes, or even fill up these holes with any other material. In this occasion, one of the most successful methods of solution has been the plane wave expansion method.

Then, let us assume that we want to compute the eigenmodes of a phononic crystal plate made of some periodic arrangement of inclusions. The PWE method consists in solving first the dispersion curves for the bulk crystal,

$$M\mathbf{u} = N\omega^2\mathbf{u} \quad (135)$$

from which we obtain the eigenvalues $\omega = \omega(\mathbf{k})$ and eigenvectors $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}$. Now, we impose boundary conditions on these modes at the top and bottom of the plate, which are the cancellation of the z component of the stress field, but this will give us a secular equation for the dispersion relation of the form

$$\det \Gamma(\omega, \mathbf{k}) = 0 \quad (136)$$

where $\Gamma(\omega, \mathbf{k})$ is certain matrix. This is in general not very efficient for the calculation of dispersion curves, since the size of the matrix Γ can be huge (this is a 3D problem) and numerically it's not easy to find the zeros of a complex determinant.

The guided mode expansion method follows a different approach [13]. First, we solve the guided modes of the homogeneous plate, and we expand the field on this basis

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}, z) = \sum_{\sigma} \sum_{\mathbf{G}} C_{\sigma\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{u}_{\sigma\mathbf{G}} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} e^{i\mathbf{G}\cdot\mathbf{r}} f_{\sigma}(z, \beta_{L\mathbf{G}}, \beta_{T\mathbf{G}}) \quad (137)$$

where $\sigma = A0, S0, SH0, A1, S1, SH1, \dots$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\sigma\mathbf{G}}$ is the polarization of each mode with wavenumber $\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{k}$. The coefficients $C_{\sigma\mathbf{G}}$ are the ones to be determined and the functions $f_{\sigma}(z, \beta_{L\mathbf{G}}, \beta_{T\mathbf{G}})$ depend on the polarization.

For a homogeneous plate the dispersion relation relates the transverse wavenumber $\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{k}$ with the propagation constants $\beta_{L\mathbf{G}}, \beta_{T\mathbf{G}}$, but these are related with frequency by means of the dispersion relation of the bulk material,

$$|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}|^2 + \beta_{X\mathbf{G}}^2 = \omega^2/c_X^2 \quad (138)$$

with $X = L, T$ in the case of an isotropic plate. Thus, given a wavenumber $\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{k}$ we can determine the corresponding eigenfrequency ω .

In this method, however, we ignore the frequency ω , thus we have the dispersion relation of Lamb waves which relates the spatial wavenumbers and then, from the dispersion relation of the bulk, we have the relationship

$$(|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}|^2 + \beta_{L\mathbf{G}}^2)c_L^2 = (|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}|^2 + \beta_{T\mathbf{G}}^2)c_T^2 \quad (139)$$

So that, given $\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}$ we can get both $\beta_{X\mathbf{G}}$, and then characterize the spatial variation of the mode. This is then a good basis to solve equation (135) by means of a variational approach.

For the case in which we are interested, which is inclusions in a plate, the elements of equation (135) are independent of z , so that in case of having a set of modes σ orthogonal in z then we would have a remarkable simplification of the problem. Unfortunately, the functions $f_\sigma(z, \beta_{L\mathbf{G}}, \beta_{T\mathbf{G}})$ are not orthogonal, although they form a basis. The coupling integrals of these modes are required for the solution of the eigenvalue problem. We expect that not so many modes branches of each mode be required for the right solution of the problem, but the literature is not clear in this sense and further research has to be done [14].

7 Discrete models for continuous resonators

Since the objective of this project is to excite a lot of modes very close in frequency each other's, we are considering working around some specific modes of the resonators which are split due to neighbour interactions. For moiré patterns this could result in the splitting of the resonant mode in many peaks due to several interactions. If this scenario is found, we could model the structure as system of N coupled resonators, simplifying dramatically the numerical calculation of the modes of the structure.

The fundamental equations describing this scenario can be fenomenologically written as

$$m_\alpha \frac{d^2 u_\alpha}{dx_\alpha^2} = -k_\alpha u_\alpha - \sum_\beta \gamma_{\alpha\beta} (u_\alpha - u_\beta) \quad (140)$$

in which we have a sistem of coupled resonators but each the resonator interact with all the others in the cluster. The eigenmodes of this system is easily found if we assume a time-harmonic dependence and we get some numerical values for the spring and masses of the resonators and, more interestingly, we need a model for the dependence of the coupling constant $\gamma_{\alpha\beta}$ as a function of the distance $R_{\alpha\beta}$ between the α and β resonators in the cluster. Once this is given, we can study the frequency splitting as a function of the different configurations of the cluster, and then optimize this quickly for our applications.

We have performed some elementary tests for the solution of the above system of equations and we are currently working on a model to describe clusters of pillars atop a thin elastic plate as this simplified model, with very promising results which will be developed within the next months.

In case of success, this model would reduce computations times in several orders of magnitude.

8 Dispersion relation for quasi-periodic structures

We have several methods for the calculation of eigenmodes of periodic distribution of scatterers, which can also be applied to random clusters of them. We know that these methods can also be applied to approximately study quasiperiodic distributions of scatterers, but we wonder if a more formal approach could be derived. In the last months we have developed a promising approach for this purpose, but still requires of some development.

Our model equation is as follows

$$\psi'' + \omega^2 \gamma(x) \psi = 0 \quad (141)$$

where γ is an arbitrary function of x . In Fourier space this is

$$-k^2 \psi(k) + \omega^2 \int \gamma(k - k') \psi(k') dk' = 0 \quad (142)$$

Now let us assume that $\gamma(x)$ is quasi-periodic, in the sense that it is expressed as

$$\gamma(x) = \gamma_b + \sum_n \xi(x - na - r \sin n\theta) \quad (143)$$

where $\xi(x)$ is a ‘‘scatterer’’ (it can be a slab, a gaussian profile, etc). Such that is zero for $|x| > a + |r|$. Using the shift property of the Fourier transform we have

$$\gamma(k) = \gamma_b \delta(k) + \xi(k) \sum_n e^{-in ka} e^{-ikr \sin n\theta} \quad (144)$$

however, we know that

$$e^{-ikr \sin n\theta} = \sum_q J_q(kr) e^{-iqn\theta} \quad (145)$$

Thus we have

$$\gamma(k) = \gamma_b \delta(k) + \xi(k) \sum_q J_q(kr) \sum_n e^{in(ka - q\theta)} \quad (146)$$

but the sum in n extends for all integers, thus

$$\gamma(k) = \gamma_b \delta(k) + \xi(k) \sum_q J_q(kr) \sum_m \delta(ka - q\theta + 2m\pi) \quad (147)$$

The Dirac deltas in the above equation makes that, when we use it to compute $\gamma(k - k')$ and integrate for all k' in equation (142), the integral will become the functions at the arguments $k' = k - (q\theta - 2m\pi)/a$, thus the eigenvalue equation becomes

$$-k^2 \psi(k) + \gamma_b \omega^2 \psi(k) + \frac{\omega^2}{a} \sum_q \sum_m J_q(G_m^q r) \xi(G_m^q) \psi(k - G_m^q) = 0 \quad (148)$$

where

$$G_m^q = (q\theta - 2m\pi)/a. \quad (149)$$

We can now make the following change of variable

$$k \rightarrow k + G_{m'}^{q'} \quad (150)$$

which defines k univocally as long as the following condition holds

$$G_m^q = G_{m'}^{q'} \leftrightarrow q = q' \wedge m = m' \quad (151)$$

the above condition holds as long as $\delta = \theta/2\pi$ do not be a rational number, which is the condition for quasi-periodicity. If the above holds, the eigenvalue equation is equivalent to

$$-(k + G_m^q)^2 \psi_{qm} + \omega^2 \sum_{q'} \sum_{m'} M_{mm'}^{qq'} \psi_{q'm'} = 0 \quad (152)$$

where

$$M_{mm'}^{qq'} = \gamma_b \delta_{mm'} \delta_{qq'} + J_{q-q'}(G_{m-m'}^{q-q'} r) \xi(G_{m-m'}^{q-q'}) \quad (153)$$

Figure 3: Example of calculation

These equations show that it is possible to obtain a dispersion relation for the aperiodic system of the form $\omega = \omega(k, \theta)$, instead of the classical spectrum $\omega = \omega(\theta)$.

We expect then that the topological properties of the system be easily studied in this way. There is however another “periodicity” of the dispersion diagram, since if we make the shift $k \rightarrow k + \ell\theta/a$, the band structure also remains unchanged.

Interestingly, the dispersion curve is periodic in both θ and ka , since if we add $\theta \rightarrow \theta + 2\ell\pi$, the factor $2q\ell\pi$ in the definition of G_m^q is absorbed by $2m\pi$ if we properly shift the sums in m . Similarly, adding $k \rightarrow k + 2\pi\ell/a$ is absorbed by the $2m\pi/a$ in the usual way.

The eigenmodes of the structure are then of the form

$$\psi(x) = e^{ikx} \sum_{q,m} \psi_{qm} e^{iq\theta/ax} e^{i2m\pi/ax} \quad (154)$$

which do not satisfy the classical Bloch form (these are not a periodic function of x times the Bloch wave).

Figure 3 shows an example of calculation of $\omega = \omega(k, \theta)$. In this case we have selected the scatterers $\gamma(x)$ as Dirac delta functions, so that $\xi(k) = \xi$. We show the projection of the band structure in the θ axis so that we get the familiar Hofstadter butterfly. However, we have more information than traditional methods based on super-cells or spectral analysis.

The convergence of this method is not clear yet, although preliminary tests with supercell calculations shows that we are in the good direction, we need to further understand the mathematical properties of these equations, and then try to extend it to the two-dimensional problem.

9 Conclusions

In summary, a considerable number of tools are available for the analysis of complex nanostructured phononic surfaces. However, each of these methods still needs to be explored for different types of materials and geometries that have been proposed in Dynamo.

Despite the fact that multiple scattering has exhibited excellent outcomes for the researchers of the consortium in the past, it has come to our attention that when the geometries of the scatterers and substrates do not adhere to some idealized situations, multiple scattering may not be the most suitable numerical tool. As a result, we have discovered other promising techniques that are worthy of exploration.

In the coming months, we will address various issues with all of the techniques presented in this document, and we will employ the most effective ones to optimize the structures in accordance with the tasks set out in work package 2.

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